

Harmful phytoplankton in Ciénaga Grande de Santa Marta: The Largest Lagoon-Delta Ecosystem in the Colombian Caribbean

Fig. 1. Location of the Ciénaga Grande de Santa Marta (CGSM), Colombia.

Ciénaga Grande de Santa Marta (CGSM) has been identified as one of the most productive coastal ecosystems at Neotropical latitudes [1]. Situated on the Caribbean coast of Colombia (Fig. 1), the wetland is bordered to the west by the Magdalena River, from which it originated. This river is regarded as the largest in the country and one of the most significant in Latin America. To the east, the CGSM lies adjacent to the foothills of the Sierra Nevada de Santa Marta, the world's highest coastal mountain range (5,800 m above sea level). At the easternmost point of its northern boundary, an inlet measuring 120 m in width and 10 m in depth, provides a direct connection between the lagoon and the Caribbean Sea. The ecosystem is dominated by rivers and characterized by a dry climate with a microtidal regime (20 to 30 cm). Annual temperatures range from 27°C to 40°C, with low average annual precipitation (531 mm) and high evapotranspiration (1,800 mm). Relative humidity varies from 77% to 83%. The strong northeast

trade winds play a key role in maintaining high productivity throughout the year. The elevated biological productivity of CGSM (990 g C m² yr⁻¹) [2] supports seven fishing communities, collectively hosting around 20,000 people, of whom approximately 3,200 depend on fishing as their primary livelihood.

The CGSM is recognized as an Important Area for the Conservation of Birds and Biodiversity (AICA/IBA) and hosts two National Natural Parks, designated in 1964 and 1977. It has held international recognition as a Ramsar Site since 1998 and as UNESCO Biosphere Reserve since 2000. In 2017, it was added to the Montreux Record, highlighting its status as a wetland whose ecological character is under significant threat [3].

The high primary productivity that sustains populations of ecologically and commercially valuable fish and invertebrates is driven by phytoplanktonic groups. Over the past two decades, artisanal fishers have harvested between 4,178 and 9,269 tons of fish, contributing an average of 35% to the total

small-scale catches in the Caribbean region [4]. The phytoplankton community comprises approximately 578 taxa, distributed among cyanobacteria (69), centric diatoms (98), pennate diatoms (191), dinoflagellates (58), chlorophyta (81), euglenophyta (64), and other groups (17) [5].

The lagoon-delta complex has been subject to various environmental stresses over almost a century, including freshwater diversion, large-scale mangrove die-off, fish kills, water contamination, and biodiversity loss [6]. Given its ecological, social, and economic importance, CGSM is one of the most studied marine socio-ecological systems in Colombia with over 1,800 bibliographic references (<https://cgsm.cemarin.org>). The ecosystem has also attracted considerable media attention, with over 874 news articles published in the last three decades, nearly 10% of which focused on mass fish kills [3]. The mortality events have often been explained by a eutrophication model, in which anoxia caused by massive plank-

Table 1. Toxic species found in Ciénaga Grande de Santa Marta.

Species	Associated Toxins	Habitat
<i>Chrysosporium (Anabaena) bergii</i> (Ostenfeld) E. Zapomelová, O. Skácelová, P. Pumann, R. Kopp & E. Janecek 2012	Anatoxins, Cylindrospermopsins, Microcystins, Saxitoxins	Brackish
<i>Coelosphaerium kuetzingianum</i> Nägeli 1849	Neurotoxins, Hepatotoxins	Freshwater
<i>Raphidiopsis (Cylindrospermopsis) raciborskii</i> Aguilera, A., Berrendero Gómez, E., Kaštovský, J., Echenique, R. O. & Salerno, G. L. 2018	Cylindrospermopsins	Freshwater
<i>Microcystis aeruginosa</i> (Kützing) Kützing 1846	Microcystins	Freshwater
<i>Planktothrix (Oscillatoria) planctonica</i> (Elenkin) Anagnostidis & Komárek 1988	Microcystins	Freshwater
<i>Raphidiopsis curvata</i> Fritsch F. E. & Rich M. F. 1930	Anatoxins, Cylindrospermopsins, Saxitoxins	Freshwater
<i>Pseudo-nitzschia pungens</i> (Grunow ex Cleve) G. R. Hasle 1993	Domoic acid	Marine
<i>Fibrocapsa japonica</i> Toriumi & Takano 1973	Reactive oxygen species, hemolytic compounds	Marine
<i>Alexandrium minutum</i> Halim 1960	Saxitoxins, neosaxitoxins, Gonyauloxins.	Marine
<i>Gonyaulax spinifera</i> (Claparède & Lachmann) Diesing 1866	Yessotoxin	Marine
<i>Prorocentrum lima</i> (Ehrenberg) F. Stein 1878	Okadaic acid	Marine
<i>Prorocentrum cordatum</i> (Ostenfeld) J. D. Dodge 1976	Fast Acting Toxins	Marine

ton growth is caused by increases in PO_4 [7].

Since other potential causes of fish mortality have not been thoroughly evaluated, the objective of this paper was to provide a comprehensive review of extant studies to identify which phytoplankton species reported in the CGSM since 1986 are potentially toxic. Of the 578 taxa reported, 12 are considered toxic; 11 appear in the IOC-UNESCO taxonomic reference list of harmful microalgae [Table 1], while *Coelosphaerium kuetzingianum* has been reported as potentially toxic to Spanish inland waters [8]. Eleven of the CGSM species are potentially toxic and 21 are classified as non-toxic harmful species [Table 2]. Additionally, six organisms were identified only at the genus level, and considered potentially harmful. Among the toxic species, six are freshwater cyanobacteria, four are dinoflagellates,

one is a diatom, and one is a raphidophyte (*Fibrocapsa japonica*), discovered in 2015 and associated with a fish kill in the CGSM.

The potential for these species to cause toxic effects in humans remains largely unexplored due to two factors. First, consumption of CGSM fishery products extends beyond the immediate region, obscuring the local impact. Second, the interface between public health and environmental management remains underdeveloped, hindering effective communication and collaboration. In Colombia, harmful algal blooms (HABs) are not considered a significant threat and receive limited attention, in contrast to the expansion of road infrastructure and planned management initiatives for the CGSM. Given the ecosystem's importance for fisheries, rigorous monitoring is necessary to ensure the safety and quality of its products.

Acknowledgements

We would like to express our sincere gratitude to the Universidad Nacional de Colombia for the opportunity to conduct research in the Ciénaga Grande de Santa Marta and to CEMarin for logistical support.

References

1. Cloern JE & Jassby AD 2008. *Ecol Lett* 11:1294–1303.
2. Hernández CA & Gocke K 1990. *An Inst Invest Mar Punta de Betín* 19:101–119. <https://boletin.invemmar.org.co/ojs/index.php/boletin/article/view/430>
3. Salzwedel H & Mancera-Pineda JE 2023. *The Colombian Ecoregion Ciénaga Grande de Santa Marta in the Public Media, 1990-2020. Editorial Unimagdalena, Santa Marta.* 82 p.
4. Rodríguez-Rodríguez JA et al 2016. *The Wetland Book II: Distribution, Description and Conservation. In Finlayson CM et al (Eds). Springer Science+Business Media BV, The Netherlands.* https://doi.org/10.1007/978-94-007-6173-5_126-1.
5. Vidal LA 2010. *Manual del fitoplancton hallado en la Ciénaga Grande de Santa Marta y cuerpos de agua aledaños. Fundación Universidad Jorge Tadeo Lozano Bogotá,* 384 p.
6. Botero L & Salzwedel H 1999. *Ocean Coastal & Management* 42:243–256.
7. Santos-Becerra LF et al 2025. *Calibration and validation of the Aerobic Mortality Risk Index (IRMA): an index for predicting mass mortality of fish due to anoxia. In Reguera B & Mertens KN (Eds) HAN 78, UNESCO, pp. 8– 9.* <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14883641>
8. Cirés S & Quesada A 2011. *Catálogo de cianobacterias planctónicas potencialmente tóxicas de las aguas continentales españolas. Dirección General del Agua de la Secretaría de Estado de Medio Rural y Agua del Ministerio de Medio Ambiente, y Medio Rural y Marino.* 85 p.

Authors

José Ernesto Mancera Pineda, Universidad Nacional de Colombia, Sede Bogotá, Colombia.

Edgar Arteaga Sogamoso (Independent investigator), Universidad Nacional de Colombia, Sede Caribe, Colombia.

Horst Salzwedel, Investigador Asociado de CEMarin, Santa Marta, Magdalena, Colombia.

Email corresponding author: jemancerap@unal.edu.co

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17256942>

Table 2. Potentially toxic species, genera and harmful non-toxic species found in Ciénaga Grande de Santa Marta.

	Species/Genera	Associated Toxins	Habitat Marine (M) Freshwater (F) Brackish (B)
T O X I C	<i>Alexandrium cf. kutnerae</i> (Balech) Balech 1985	unknown	M
	<i>Alexandrium cf. minutum</i> Halim 1960	Saxitoxins	M
	<i>Anabaena cf. sphaerica var. tenuis</i> G. S. West 1907	unknown	F
	<i>Anabaena cf. spiroides</i> Klebahn 1895	Anatoxin-a	F
	<i>Dolichospermum (Anabaena) cf. spiroides</i> (Klebahn) Wacklin, L. Hoffmann & Komárek 2009	Anatoxins	F
	<i>Anabaenopsis cf. cunningtonii</i> W. R. Taylor 1932	unknown	F
	<i>Gonyaulax cf. diegensis</i> Kofoid 1911	unknown	M
	<i>Gonyaulax cf. rotundata</i> Rampi 1952	unknown	M
	<i>Microcystis cf. viridis</i> (A. Braun) Lemmermann 1903	Microcystins	F
	<i>Planktothrix (Oscillatoria) cf. agardhii</i> (Gomont) Anagnostidis & Komárek 1988	Microcystins, Anatoxin, Saxitoxins.	F
	<i>Planktothrix cf. isothrix</i> (Skuja) Komárek & Komárková 2004	Microcystins, Anatoxin, Saxitoxins	F
	<i>Aphanizomenon sp.</i>	Anatoxin, Saxitoxins, Cylindrospermopsins	F
	<i>Coelosphaerium sp.</i>	Neurotoxins, Hepatoxins	F
	<i>Cylindrospermopsis sp.</i>	Cylindrospermopsins	F
	<i>Cylindrospermum sp.</i>	Cylindrospermopsins	F
	<i>Phormidium sp.</i>	Alkaloid	F
<i>Pseudo-nitzschia sp.</i>	Domoic acid	M	
N O N -T O X I C	<i>Cerataulina pelagica</i> (Cleve) Hendey 1937		M
	<i>Protodinium cf. simplex</i> Lohmann 1908		M, F
	<i>Tripos furca</i> (Ehrenberg) F.Gómez 2013		M
	<i>Chaetoceros tenuissimus f. beisugensis</i> Gogorev & Kovaleva 2010		M
	<i>Coscinodiscus centralis</i> Ehrenberg 1839		M
	<i>Guinardia striata</i> (Stolterfoth) Hasle 1996		M
	<i>Oxyrrhis marina</i> Dujardin 1841		M
	<i>Prorocentrum micans</i> Ehrenberg 1834		M
	<i>Sundstroemia setigera</i> (Brightwell) Medlin 2021		M
	<i>Anabaenopsis circularis</i> (G. S. West) V. V. Miller 1923		F
	<i>Anabaena oscillarioides</i> Bory ex Bornet & Flahault 1886		M, F
	<i>Anabaena sphaerica</i> Bornet & Flahault 1886		F
	<i>Anabaena torulosa</i> Lagerheim ex Bornet & Flahault 1886		M, F
	<i>Lynghya martensiana f. rupestris</i> Frémy 1930		M, B
	<i>Microcystis densa</i> Schiller 1956		F
	<i>Microcystis marginata</i> (Meneghini) Kützing 1846		F
	<i>Microcystis robusta</i> (H. W. Clark) Nygaard 1925		F
	<i>Gonyaulax digitalis</i> (Pouchet) Kofoid 1911		M
	<i>Gonyaulax polyedra</i> F. Stein 1883*		M
	<i>Gonyaulax scrippsae</i> Kofoid 1911		M
<i>Sourniaea diacantha</i> (Meunier) H.Gu., K.N.Mertens, Zhun Li & H.H.Shin 2020		M	

*) now *Lingulaulax polyedra* (F.Stein) M.J.Head, K.N.Mertens & R.A.Fensome 2024, can produce yessotoxins.